

PROCEEDINGS

JOIN CONVENTION BANDUNG (JCB) 2021

December 1ST – 3rd 2021

This is ichnofabric analysis!

Ery Arifullah¹⁾

¹⁾Department of Geology, Universitas Muhammadiyah Kalimantan Timur

Abstract

I have developed ichnofabric studies using several variables, such as ichnofossil association, bioturbation index, ichnodiversity, number of behaviors, penetration depth, and diameter of burrows. There are different approaches to ichnofossil systematics. I use statistical methods to resolve the pattern of ichnofabric variables. Ichnofabric analysis should involve paleocurrent and sedimentological analysis. One of the uniqueness of the ichnofabric analysis is the release of ichnofossil from Seilacher's ichnofacies model. Interpretation of the results of ichnofabric analysis by adopting paleoecological principles. Thus, ichnofossil can achieve optimal resolution in the study of depositional systems.

Introduction

Ichnofabric is those aspects of the texture and internal structure of the bed resulting from all phases of bioturbation (Ekdale and Bromley, 1983). By that definition, ichnofossil is a biogenic sedimentary structure. An ichnofabric unit is a substrate unit in which some ichnofossils with a certain ichnodiversity dominate by specific behavior formed almost simultaneously (Arifullah, 2019; Arifullah et al. 2021). Consequently, each ichnofabric unit cover ichnofossil, degree of bioturbation (BI), ichnodiversity (ID), behavior (NB) with addition penetration depth (PD), and burrow diameter (DM) (see Arifullah, 2019).

Ichnofossil commonly receives a paleontologic or zoologic connotation. Because of this aspect, traces are often given short shrift by sedimentologists. This situation is unfortunate and indeed unfair to the study of sediments because the contained *lebensspuren* are sedimentary structures (albeit biologically formed). Ichnofossil often supplies evidence of sedimentological conditions superior to information gained only by studying physical structures (see Arifullah, 2019).

How to use Seilacher's models is not without controversy. This model did not intend to be a norm (see Frey, 1975; Goldring, 1993). But the opposite happened. This resulted in ichnofossil being unable to reach its best resolution. For example, certain ichnofossil is forced to be grouped into specific ichnofacies associations in the Seilacher model. As a result, ichnofossil is locked in a Seilacher model of ichnofacies.

Ichnofabric variables

Understanding the pattern of ichnofossil distribution in the outcrops can be done (Arifullah et al. 2016, Figure 2). In this way, I recognize the relationship between ichnofossil distribution and some levels bounding surfaces such as set, coset, or composite sets of cross-bedding and also a determination of lateral accretion surfaces.

The three-dimensional view of ichnofossil is essential to characterize the general morphology (see Arifullah et al. 2021, Fig. 3), the orientation of bedding surface (shaft or tunnel or both), and branching or unbranched or cross-cutting relationship. I integrated all of them with the burrow fill (active fill/meniscate backfill or passive fill)

and the burrow lining for the taxonomy of ichnofossils (see Knaust, 2012).

In addition, the naming of ichnofossil association in ichnofabric unit is based on recognizing the dominant ichnotaxon which presence is higher than 50% compared to other ichnotaxon/ichnotaxa (Pickerill and Narbonne, 1995). Consequently, the name of the ichnofabric unit is based on the dominant ichnofossil and followed by BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM (see Arifullah et al. 2021, Figure 2).

Despite many ichnotaxa being identified but only a few ichnotaxa predominate. In the case of Kutai Basin, only 17% (6 ichnotaxa) of total ichnotaxa appear in 91% ichnofabric units (Arifullah et al. 2021). Those six ichnotaxa are the principal ichnofossil association in Kutai Basin. Those findings are a unique approach in ichnofabric studies.

Bioturbation index (BI) reflects the ratio of biogenic and physical sediment structures in the ichnofabric unit. BI is how much physical structure of sediment is left in the ichnofabric unit because of animal rework (Rhoads, 1975). Calculating of BI by using BI scheme that Drosser and Bottjer developed (see Drosser and Bottjer, 1986, Fig. 1 and 1989, Figure 1).

Ichnodiversity (ID) is the number of ichnotaxon variations within the ichnofabric unit (Buatois and Mángano, 2013). ID has nothing to do with fauna diversity. If three ichnotaxon are identified in the ichnofabric unit, then the ID score is three.

The number of behavior (NB) means the number of habits of an organism to keep internal conditions constant against fluctuating external environmental conditions (Vallon et al. 2015). I deciphered modes of behavior in the ichnofabric units by looking at the ichnofossil structure. Thus, we found: (1) how animals build ichnofossil structures, either by the intrusion, compressive, excavation, or backfill processes (Bromley, 1996); (2) the general direction of animal movement based on the burrow orientation (Arifullah, 2019); and (3) the duration of the colonization window, which can be inferred from the morphological complexity of the ichnofossil.

Penetration depth (PD) is the penetration of an animal to the substrate. Paleoecological factors regulate the PD, such as oxygenation (Pearson and Rosenberg, 1978), fluctuations of salinity (Sanders et al. 1965), and temperature (Johnson, 1965), which are common in the transition zone.

The burrow diameter (DM) shows the relative size of the burrow's shaft and tunnel. Measuring the DM should determine the burrow lining and the burrow fill (Arifullah, 2019). Actual DM is the diameter of the burrow fill. In addition, the scores tabulation of PD and DM had been created (see Arifullah et al. 2021, Table 2 and 3).

The scores of BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM in the basin analysis could be displayed by histogram. The histogram demonstrated the skewness that the trend of BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM scores could be seen (see Arifullah et al. 2021, Figure 8).

PROCEEDINGS

JOIN CONVENTION BANDUNG (JCB) 2021

December 1ST – 3rd 2021

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Are BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM important? If only some parts were necessary, several variables must be maintained, and others must be discarded. However, this is the subjective way. Consequently, PCA is applied to keep the original data and simplify that five variables into 2 or 3 variables without reducing the original structure significantly. In this way, BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM were reduced become PC-1 (positively correlated with BI, ID, and NB) and PC-2 (positively correlated with PD and DM). Consequently, each ichnofabric unit has scored in PC-1 and PC-2 (see Arifullah, 2021, Table 1). In this proceeding, further explanation of the PCA could be read in paper ID-417 (Arifullah, 2021).

PC's curves and maps

Since each ichnofabric unit has scored in PC-1 and PC-2, it could be drawn as two curves embrace the outcrop's stratigraphic section. It looks like a wireline logging curve. The curves' interrelationship could be analyzed further (e.g., depositional processes and paleoecological event) but should be supported by lithofacies data in the stratigraphic section (e.g., Arifullah, 2019, Figure IV-8) for optimal interpretation. Furthermore, based on PC's scores of each outcrop (Arifullah, 2019, Table III-14), the PC's maps were created (e.g., Arifullah, 2019, Figure III-56).

Paleocurrent analysis

Paleocurrent maps were created (e.g., Arifullah, 2019, Figure III-46 and III-47). These maps were overlayed to PC's maps to create paleogeographic maps (Arifullah, 2019, Figure IV-1 and IV-2).

Discussion

Ichnofossil as paleoecological function

Ichnofossil is affiliated implicitly with the number of paleoecological factors such as oxygenation (Rhoads and Morse, 1971), salinity fluctuation (Sanders et al. 1965) and temperature fluctuation (Johnson, 1965), community structure (Levinton, 1977; Reise, 1979), food supplies (Bambach, 1983), the way organisms get food (Purdy, 1964; Rhoads and Young, 1970), sedimentology (Howard, 1975; Arifullah, 2019), substrate stability (Bromley, 1996), population strategies and disturbance (Arifullah, 2019).

Ichnofossil association can be used to understand paleoecology (see Arifullah et al. 2021, Table 4). Concerning about survival, Arifullah et al. (2021) said:

For survival, the trace maker is more effective in creating ichnofossil structures with almost negligible variation for optimal survival efforts. It concentrates on building essentially the same structure in fluctuating and unpredictable paleoecological conditions.

Paleoecological hierarchy

I think using PCA just not discard some variables and maintain others because of their importance but PCA resolving the paleoecological hierarchy. BI, ID, and NB suggest innovation, mobility, and fauna behavior (ichnodisparity) controlled by food supply (Arifullah, 2019). PD and DM suggest space utilization controlled by a fluctuation of paleosalinity and paleotemperature. It looks like the paleoecological hierarchy that BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM are lower hierarchy than food supply and fluctuation of paleosalinity and paleotemperature.

Paleogeography

Kutai Basin's NW-SE or W-E paleocurrent trend correlates with ichnodisparity and space utilization trends (Arifullah, 2021). Consequently, the ichnodisparity and space utilization map is the potential to delineate the paleodepositional trend. Overlaying those maps will create paleogeographic maps.

Seilacher's model

Paleobathymetry is only one of the dozen parameters of paleoecological factors (Ekdale, 1988; Savrda and Bottjer, 1994). In addition, the same ichnofossil association can occur in shallow to deep marine zones (Arifullah et al. 2021, Table 5). Consequently, Seilacher's model is not a norm, just a case study, and cannot be used for paleobathymeter. This is a chance to create our own unique ichnofacies model because every depositional environment is unique.

Conclusion

Ichnofabric analysis is an approach that places ichnofossil as sedimentary structure. Consequently, ichnofossil should receive attention equal to that devoted to structures developed by physical processes. Since paleoecology in a particular place and time is unique, creating our ichnofabric models (ichnofossil association, bioturbation index, ichnodiversity, number of behaviors, penetration depth, burrow diameter) could be presented as semi-quantitative models. Freeing ichnotaxa from Seilacher's ichnofacies models should be done for the best interpretation of the depositional system. However, it should be supported by lithofacies, paleocurrent, and paleontology data.

References

- Arifullah, E., 2019, Ph.D., Dissertation, Institut Teknologi Bandung (Text in Indonesia). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3992482>.
- Arifullah, E., Chandra, A., Setiaji, R.A., Zaim, Y., Aswan., Djuhaeni, 2016, *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Kebumihan Ke-9: Peran Penelitian Ilmu Kebumihan Dalam Pemberdayaan Masyarakat*, Universitas Gadjah Mada, 700-703. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3992590>.
- Arifullah, E., Zaim, Y., Aswan., Djuhaeni, 2021, *Journal of Mathematical and Fundamental Sciences* **53**, 285-304. <https://doi.org/10.5614/j.math.fund.sci.2021.53.2.8>.
- Bromley, R. G., 1996, *Springer Science+Business Media B.V.*
- Buatois, L. A, and Mángano, G.M, 2013, *Lethaia* **46**, 281–292.
- Droser, M. L, and Bottjer, D.J, 1986, *Journal of Sedimentary Research* **56** (4), 558–559.
- Droser, M. L, and Bottjer, D.J, 1989, *Palaaios* **4** (6), 598–604.
- Ekdale, A. A, 1988, *Palaaios*, Determining Paleobathymetry **3** (5), 464–472.
- Ekdale, A. A, and Bromley, R.G, 1983, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark* **31**, 107–119.
- Frey, R. W, 1975, *In The Study of Trace Fossils: A Synthesis of Principles, Problems and Procedures in Ichnology*, Frey R.W (ed), Springer - Verlag, 15–38.
- Goldring, R, 1993, *Palaaios* **8**, 403–405.
- Howard, J. D, 1975, *In The Study of Trace Fossils: A Synthesis of Principles, Problems and Procedures in Ichnology*, Frey, R. W (ed), Springer - Verlag, 131–146.

PROCEEDINGS

JOIN CONVENTION BANDUNG (JCB) 2021

December 1ST – 3rd 2021

- Johnson, R.G, 1965, *Limnology and Oceanography* **10**, 114–120.
- Knaust, D., 2012, *In Trace Fossil as Indicators of Sedimentary Environments*, Knaust, D., and Bromley, R.G (eds), Elsevier BV, 79-102.
- Levinton, J.S, 1977, *In Ecology of Marine Benthos*, Coull, B.C (ed), Univ. South Carolina Press, 191–227.
- Pearson, T.H, and Rosenberg, R, 1978, *Oceanogr. Mar. Biol. Ann. Rev* **16**, 229–311.
- Pickerill, R. K, and Narbonne, G.M, 1995, *Ichnos* **4**, 53–69.
- Purdy, E. G, 1964, *In Approaches to Paleoecology*, Imbrie, J and Newell, N (eds), John Wiley and Sons, Inc, 238–271.
- Reise, K, 1979, *Helgoländer Wiss. Meeresunters* **32**, 55–72.
- Rhoads, D.C, 1975, *In The Study of Trace Fossils: A Synthesis of Principles, Problems and Procedures in Ichnology*, Frey, R.W (ed), Springer - Verlag, 147–169.
- Rhoads, D.C, and Young, D.K, 1970, *Journal of Marine Research* **28** (2), 150–78.
- Rhoads, D.C, and Morse, J.W, 1971, *Lethaia* **4**, 413–428.
- Sanders, H. L, Mangelsdorf, P.C, and Hampson, G.R, 1965, *Limnology and Oceanography* **10**, 216–229.
- Savrda, C. E, and Bottjer, D.J, 1994, *In Orbital Forcing and Cyclic Sequences*, de Boer, P. L and Smith, D. G (eds), *Spec. Publs Int. Ass. Sediment.*, **19**, 195–210.
- Vallon, L. H, Rindsberg, A.K, and Bromley, R.G, 2015, *Geodinamica Acta* **28** (1–2), 1–17.